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D7.5 User Forum and Organisation report on activities

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Abstract

The IPERION HS (IPHS) User Forum represents a supportive learning and engagement environment called Heritage Science Academy. The HS Academy (#HSAcademy) is an online environment designed to support a global community of users and potential users of IPHS facilities, through online seminars and training videos, as well as through social media. The aim of the HS Academy is to promote the IPHS facilities and excellent science carried out through TransNational Access (TNA) projects and joint research activities, and also to engage the wider heritage science community in current issues related to heritage science policy and the wider societal issues that impact on the development of heritage science, from climate to social change. The HS Academy promotes interdisciplinarity through a holistic engagement with topics across STEM and SSH disciplines. The HS Academy webinar series has run monthly since April 2021 and Current topics lecture series since September 2022. We also conducted an extensive questionnaire on HS demographic between November 2022 – February 2023. In total we collected 413 responses to the questionnaire. All these activities have high online visibility, both through the IPHS website and through related social media, and a truly global engagement is visible. An HS Academy anchor has been established on the professional social networking platform LinkedIn, which has also been an important tool. The LinkedIn Online Forum explores the links with the LinkedIn interest groups, where further interest in IPERION HS services can be developed.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
HS	Heritage Science

1 HS Academy Lecture series

The series of online lectures “Current Topics in Heritage Science” are part of HS Academy training activities, delivered through the Heritage Science On-line Forum.

1.1 Structure and format

The “Current Topics in Heritage Science” lecture series was launched by HS Academy team, to provide non-academic training online on fundamental aspects of heritage science, such as techniques and methodologies, as well as on specific heritage typologies and other topics of interest to the heritage science community but not restricted to it. The lectures are complementary to the standard HS Academy webinar series. Their main target are emerging professionals, such as students, but also advanced conservators, curators, restorers, and heritage scientists.

The lectures were held **online** (on Zoom webinar platform) on the third Thursday afternoon (3 pm CET/CEST) of the month during Edition 1. This was changed to the fourth Thursday afternoon (3 pm CET/CEST) of the month during Edition 2. Each speaker’s presentation had a duration of about 30 minutes (recorded and later available on YouTube), followed by at least 15 minutes of Q&A session (45 minutes in total).

The general structure of the lectures was:

- Introduction to the topic (about 10 minutes)
- Methodology description (about 10 minutes)
- Case studies and applications (about 10 minutes).

1.2 Organizing team

The online lecture series were launched by a team of emerging professionals of HS Academy, working on international projects in the field of heritage science. The team, called also Emerging Professionals Editorial Board, was originally composed of 6 members who were in charge of the 1st edition (2022-2023). For the 2nd edition (2023-2024), the team was composed of 4 members. The full list of members working on the delivery of “Current Topics in Heritage Science” lecture series is reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of the organizing team

Edition 1*	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tjaša Rijavec, University of Ljubljana 2. Fabiana Di Gianvincenzo, University of Ljubljana 3. Hassan Ebeid, University of Ljubljana 4. Moira Bertasa, CNR-INO 5. Diego Quintero, CNR-INO 6. Antonina Chaban, CNR-INO
Edition 2*	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tjaša Rijavec, University of Ljubljana 2. Fabiana Di Gianvincenzo, University of Ljubljana 3. Diego Quintero, CNR-INO 4. Antonina Chaban, CNR-INO

*Mentors: Matija Strlic, Jana Striova and Laura Benassi

Figure 1: Screenshot of the IPERION HS webpage, dedicated to the lecture series; below: Screenshots of video recordings of the lectures of Edition 1 (lecture 1 on the left and lecture 10 on the right), available on E-RIHS YouTube channel

The lecture series required 6 months of preparation before launch. The activities, which included topics and speaker selection, organization and schedule as well as preparation of graphics and other materials for promotion, were carried out by the organizing team and managed by the IPERION HS coordination office.

1.3 Programme and statistics of online lecture series

The following table reports the full list of the topics, speakers, as well as numbers of participants (live attendees and post-event online views, respectively) for lectures delivered by M48 (IPHS project). The speakers were based in 14 different countries, mainly in Europe (Italy, Spain, Greece, France, Poland and UK) but also from other countries such as Brazil and South Africa.

Table 2: Attendance data for the Lecture Series

Lecture	Date	Speaker	Topic	Live participants	Post-event YouTube views M48 IPHS (accessed on 11.03.24)
Edition 1 (2022-2023)					
#01	15.09.22	Katrien Keune	From model to painting: added values and limitations of reconstruction and model-based research	104	470
#02	20.10.22	Vivi Tornari	Principles of holographic interferometry for non-destructive subsurface examination	114	404
#03	17.11.22	Zvi Koren	Chromatographic analyses of molluskan purple pigments	72	45
#04	15.12.22	Josep Grau-Bove	Past, present and future of citizen heritage science	63	191
#05	19.01.23	Sahra Talamo	Timing the spread of creative innovations by Homo sapiens and Neanderthals using the radiocarbon dating method	65	178
#06	16.02.23	Verônica Teixeira	Sirius – a powerful tool to study ancient materials with synchrotron light	67	143
#07	16.03.23	Caroline Solazzo	Proteomics in the cultural heritage field: the case of fibrous proteins	111	150
#08	20.04.23	Daniel O’Flynn	X-ray imaging in cultural heritage: the past to the present	210	312
#09	18.05.23	Michela Botticelli	Ethical sampling: from 'seed to fruit' and beyond	82	111
#10	22.06.23	Livio De Luca	Towards cathedrals of digital data and multidisciplinary knowledge in heritage science	83	250
Total for Edition 1:				971	2254

Edition 2 (2022-2023)						
#01	26.10.23	Piotr Targowski	Optical Coherence Tomography for examination of artworks	82	128	
#02	30.11.23	Dante Abate	AI in the Loop: Enhancing Cultural Property Protection through Intelligent Methods	128	68	
#03	15.12.23	Altug Hazosbek	Chronological Tools: Dating Human Evolutionary History	58	65	
#04	25.01.24	Emma Karoune	Open and FAIR Science with a case study from the FAIR Phytoliths project	53	26	
#05	22.02.24	Bernhard Blümich	Portable NMR for structural diagnostic in heritage science	120	29	
Total for Editions 1 and 2, at M48 (11.03.24):				1412	2570	

1.4 Statistics and impact of the online lecture series “Current Topics in Heritage Science”

The general statistical data, based on the registration form, ZOOM webinar reports and post-event analysis survey of **Lectures 1-10 of Edition 1** are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: First Edition attendance data

Statistics of 1 st Edition (2022-2023)	Average	Lowest	Highest
Number of participants	97.7	63	210
Number of countries of affiliation	34.2	23	57
Average satisfaction (from 1=poor to 10=excellent)	8.9	8.5	9.1

The total number of participants, registered to attend the lectures of Edition 1 (10 lectures) and Edition 2 (5 lectures), 15 training events in total by M48 is of 2565. Figure 2 illustrates the geographical distribution of registered participants from the total of 70 countries. The most represented countries of the registered participants for the delivered online lectures (15) were the following: Italy (17%), Poland (11%), Spain (10%), Malta (9%), Slovenia (5%) and UK (5%). Average participation rate (live participants vs registered participants) is of 55%.

Figure 2: Above: Geographical distribution of registered participants from 70 countries

Participants of the lecture series, who filled in the anonymous post-event analysis survey by January 1, 2024, identified themselves with various scientific communities, including domains of heritage science and conservation science (15%), conservation and restoration (15%), fundamental science (11%) and new domains for IPERION HS TNA access users: social sciences and humanities (23%); Archaeology (15%); Built environment (8%); Palaeoanthropology and palaeontology (1%), Figure 3.

Figure 3: Scientific domains of “Current Topics in Heritage Science” participants, as stated through the anonymous post-event surveys, based on data from 15 online events (M48)

Figure 4 illustrates the statistical analysis of suggested topics (A) and some examples of individual feedback by participants, provided anonymously (B).

Figure 4: Above: Topics of interest and impact of the “Current Topics in Heritage Science Series” training events series: A) analysis of suggested topics of interest. Below: Topics of interest and impact of the “Current Topics in Heritage Science Series” training events series: B) individual comments. The data was derived from the analysis of 15 online events (M48)

Q4 Any further comments?

- Source: post-event survey
- *I really appreciated the lectures being at a time that I could join easily (based in the US). Thank you for taking that into consideration (lecture 1, Ed.1)*
 - *Thank you for sharing your knowledge in Heritage Science with us! (lecture 1, Ed. 1)*
 - *Excellent general overview with a great, very experienced speaker. I've been working in the field for a long while now, so some of the material was basic for me, but some of the case studies were new, which I really enjoyed. Really well done, and a good use of an hour of my time (lecture 8, Ed.1)*
 - *Keep up the great work! (most of the lectures)*
 - *Thank you for the great opportunity to follow these talks online (lecture 9, Ed. 1)*

The experience of providing online training in the form of “Current Topics in Heritage Science” series”, statistics and feedback analysis results, as well as adopted procedures by the organizing team, will be used for the organization of future training activities of HS Academy by E-RIHS. The detailed information about the developed framework of activities for the launch of the series and detailed guidelines for the delivery of each single training event of the series will be provided in D2.5 of E-RIHS IP: Guidelines for the E-RIHS Central Hub Management Practices.

2 HS Academy Webinar series

IPERION HS and E-RIHS are organizing a series of webinars, a key source of state-of-the-art information on #HeritageScience research, facilities, policy and impact. The series contributes to the development of a vibrant heritage science community and is intended for anyone involved in interdisciplinary #heritage research.

The monthly webinars were typically 30 min long, followed by Q&A. The webinar series (<http://www.iperionhs.eu/webinar-series/#>) is a key source of state-of-the-art information on heritage science research, facilities, policy and impact. It contributes to the development of a vibrant heritage science community and is intended for anyone involved in interdisciplinary heritage research.

The webinar series programme was developed by the Editorial Committee consisting of:

1. Marta Castillejo
2. Hilde De Clercq
3. Victor Etgens
4. Adam Gibson
5. Alison Heritage
6. Francois Mirambet
7. Costanza Miliani
8. Luca Pezzati
9. Jana Striova
10. Matija Strlic

Organization and promotion are developed and carried out in collaboration with IPERION HS Work Package 8 (Central support activities). Typically, this involves planning, establishment of speaker contacts, confirmation and briefing, but also a teaser video production, social media engagement, ZOOM platform setup and technical support, as well as post-event audience engagement and feedback collection. A specific hashtag has been created and associated with these activities (#HSAcademy).

The training material is available as part of the HS Academy as:

- YouTube collection: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCuN9HLbVXleJtOxCjiYjHyw/videos>
- HS Academy website: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/hs-academy-resources/>

Figure 5: HS Academy Webinar website – all webinars are announced as a teaser video, on this website, and video recordings are available post-event

The webinar recordings are video-edited at ZVKDS/UL and uploaded to the E-RIHS YouTube video channel.

In addition to the training material produced on the basis of the webinar activity, a stand-alone training video was produced on the topic of Collaborative Research Training (Figure 6).

Figure 6: The Collaborative research training video start frame

We looked at the participation at the events that took place since November 2021 until the end of December 2022. Altogether there were 11 webinars organized exclusively by HS Academy webinar

series, 3 events that were conducted as part of user meetings, and 3 events that were conducted in collaboration with JPI CH (Table 4).

Table 4: Dates and titles of IPHS webinars

9.11.2021	Palaeontology research and IPERION HS
7.12.2021	Archaeology and IPERION HS
2022	
11.01.2022	Understanding laser interactions with materials in HS
8.2.2022	New synchrotron light sources and paleontological studies
8.3.2022	Remote sensing-based approach for Cultural Heritage interpretation and monitoring
5.4.2022	Hyperspectral and multispectral imaging in HS
10.5.2022	Developing European Collaboration in Heritage Science
14.6.2022	Fair data. The challenge of interoperability in Heritage Science
13.9.2022	European OMC - Climate change and cultural heritage
10.10.2022	Evaluation and monitoring of ESFRI infrastructures
8.11.2022	Olfactory heritage - preserving the smell of sites and collections

The HS Webinars were averaging around 140 participants per event (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Participation at HS Academy webinars

In 2023, the webinars featured user meetings (Table 1). They took place between May and September 2023. They averaged about 50 participants (Figure 8).

Table 5: HS Academy User Meetings

Date	Name	Speaker/s
30.05.2023	IPERION HS TNA Fixlab & Archlab	Ina Reiche and Thomas Romain
13.6.2023	IPERION HS TNA Fixlab & Archlab	Lucrezia Milillo and Marya Albrecht
12.9.2023	IPERION HS TNA Fixlab & Archlab	Diego Quintero and Vanessa Nunes

Figure 8: Participation at HS Academy User Meetings

In the second half of 2023, the webinars were conducted together with JPI CH (Table 6). The webinars took place between October and December. They averaged between 20-30 participants (Figure 9).

Table 6: Dates and presents of the HS Academy/JPI webinars

Date	Name	Speaker/s
10.10.2023	JPI-CH webinar 1	Manuela Romagnoli
14.11.2023	JPI-CH webinar 2	Christiana Nunes
12.12.2023	JPI-CH webinar 3	Frédérique Duyrat, Andrew Meadows, Pere Pau Ripollès

Figure 9: Participation data for the HS Academy/JPI Webinars

Furthermore, we analysed the post-event user interactions. We looked at the views of the recording on the YouTube platform and compared the different activities for the HS Academy Webinars and Current Topics Lectures (Table 7).

Table 7: Average views between January 2022 – December 2023. Orange: HS Academy Webinars; green: HS Current topics lectures

3 HS Academy LinkedIn platform

The LinkedIn platform “Heritage Science Online Forum”, supported by HS Academy, represents a growing community of professionals, and currently has 2715 users. It has been growing at a 51.6% rate in the period between October 2022- to October 2023. The amplification rate percentage, which represents the rate at which the followers take the content and share it through their network, represented 16.4%.

Figure 10: IPERION HS Academy Online Forum on LinkedIn represents the online User Forum as defined in Task 7.2.

The LinkedIn Online Forum explores links with the LinkedIn interest groups, where further interest in IPERION HS services could be developed. The structure of the followers in the period between July 2022 and July 2023 is represented below in graphs (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Map with representation of countries of LinkedIn users.

The analysis of followers (Figure 12) revealed that the highest percentage of them works in industries such as Higher Education (18.8 %) followed by Research Services (14.4%), Museums, Historical Sites, and Zoos (10.9%), Museums (6.5%), Government Administration (5.6%), Architecture and Planning (3.8%), Artists and Writers (3.7%), Retail Art Supplies (2.2%), Non-profit

Organizations (2.1%), Education Administration Program (1.5%). Their main job functions include Research (17.3%), Education (15.5%), Arts and Design (14.3%), Business Development (5.2%), Operations (4%), Community and Social Services (2.6%), Administrative (2.3%), Media and Communication (2.3%), Program and Project Management (2.1%), Engineering (2%).

The analysis of visitors revealed that highest percentage of visitors comes from Research Services industry (18,5%), followed by Museums, Historical Sites, and Zoos (14,3%), Higher Education (11,9%), Architecture and Planning (8,4%), Artists and Writers (4,5%), Government Administration (4,3%), Chemical Manufacturing (3,1%), Civil Engineering (2,6%), Retail Art Supplies (2,4%), Software Development (2%). Their main job functions include Research (20,2%), Education (15%), Arts and Design (8,8%), Business Development (4,6%), Operations (2,6%), Administrative (2,5%), Program and Project Management (2,3%), Media and Communication (2,2%), Marketing (2%), Community and Social Services (2%).

Figure 12: Online User Forum users and followers' data

4 HS Academy Workshops

The HS Academy workshops are events to engage professionals in an interdisciplinary discussion on the relevant topics of interest for the heritage science community. The workshops consist of presentations and discussion sessions. The events can be held in presence, online or in a hybrid form.

The HS Academy workshops engage professionals and students from all heritage related backgrounds, for an intensive discussion on a specific topic of interest. It is possibility to apply for involvement in the workshop as a speaker or as a participant.

The speakers and their topics of presentation were selected by the Scientific Committee, on the basis of the criteria reported in the 1st announcement. The participants are admitted to the workshop by the Scientific Committee, following the selection procedure.

The events were hosted by IPERION HS partners in Ljubljana (Slovenia) and Bologna (Italy), in a hybrid form. The 1st HS Academy Workshop was held in a hybrid form (in presence and online) on October 25, 2023, during the 4th interim meeting of IPERION HS project in Ljubljana, Slovenia. The 2nd HS Academy Workshop, in a form of Working Group Meeting, was held in a hybrid form (in presence and online) on January 25 and January 26, 2024, in Bologna, Italy.

4.1 Workshop in Ljubljana

Workshop on Research infrastructures and education: the case of heritage science within the 4th IPERION HS interim meeting was held in Ljubljana (SI) on 25 October, 2023, between 14:00-18:00 (local time, CEST). The inspiration behind the workshop theme was the case for closer involvement of research infrastructures (RIs) in education has been made repeatedly by ESFRI, claiming that the new ERA requires the development of an “interconnected environment of which RIs are an important element is not restricted only to research, it extends also to other areas like education, innovation, health and others.” While RIs contribute to education by providing specialised training and access to students, it is less clear how the desired “interconnectedness” could be enshrined more deeply in the conceptualisation as well as in the process of education at the level of higher education. The ESFRI White paper from 2020 puts forward the idea of “knowledge innovation hubs in which RIs are embedded in regional education”. The notion of “promoting science and scientific careers to young people by stronger structured collaborations between RIs and universities leading to greater mobility and exchange programmes between these sectors” would require strategic and operational collaboration and implies the involvement of RIs in the development of educational programmes, e.g. on advisory levels, through staff secondments and other mechanisms, in addition to provision of access for the purpose of student research and provision of specialised training, including hands-on research training.

Table 8: Attendance at the HA Academy workshop in Ljubljana

	Role	Number
Day 1, Oct 25, 2023	Speakers	10 (7 in presence and 3 online)
	In-presence participants (non-speakers and members of the organizing team)	55 (6)
	online participants	75
Total present at the meeting		140

PROGRAMME

14:00 Workshop start

14:00-14:10 Matija Strlič, University of Ljubljana: Welcome

14:10-14:30 Jana Kolar, CERIC: Training and ecosystem development - CERIC's approach

14:30-14:50 Laura Angeletti, CERIC: Italian ERIC Forum and RI careers

14:50-15:10 Sally Chambers, CESAER: Infrastructures and synergies to help tackle local and global challenges

15:10-15:30 Break

15:30-15:50 Carlo Bianchini, University of Pavia: Italian Research and Knowledge Infrastructure dedicated to Cultural Heritage

15:50-16:10 Isidora Stankovic, Universite Paris 1: Una Europa doctoral program in cultural heritage

16:10-16:30 Nataša Poklar, University of Ljubljana: EUTOPIA and Research Infrastructures

16:30-16:50 Break

16:50-17:10 Rocco Mazzeo, University of Bologna: Conservation science education at University of Bologna

17:10-17:30 Josep Grau, UCL Institute for Cultural Heritage: UK EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training in Heritage Science

17:30-17:50 Vincent Detalle, Universite Cergy Paris: The last 5 years of master research trainings supported by "La Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine" in France

18:00 Workshop end

4.2 Workshop in Bologna

The workshop in a form of working group meeting on “Research infrastructures and heritage science career paths” was jointly organized by the IPERION and E-RIHS IP and held on January 25- 26, 2024, at the University of Bologna, Department of Chemistry G. Ciamician, Via F. Selmi 7, Bologna (Italy). Its aim was to examine the provision of heritage science education, the skills necessary for employment in different heritage science sectors and employers, as well as the typical heritage science career paths.

The event was held in a hybrid form (online and in-presence) on January 25th and only in presence on January 26th. On January 25th, 12 speakers (professionals working in the field of heritage science education) delivered presentations in presence and online (streamed live on Microsoft Teams) on the topics related to the state-of-the-art in the field of heritage science education, skillset of heritage scientists, the role of research infrastructures and analysis of heritage science career paths. On January 26th, the working group produced the draft of the final document “Enabling diverse career pathways to enhance heritage science capacities - a call to action”.

The topics for presentations were selected upon a call for proposals. The participants (Table 9) were admitted upon selection process. The presentations (total of 12) and participants (3 in presence and 81 online, total of 84) were selected by the Scientific Committee of the working group meeting event.

Table 9: Attendance at the HA Academy workshop in Bologna

	Role	Number
Day 1, Jan 25, 2024	Speakers	12 (9 in presence and 3 online)
	In-presence participants (non-speakers and members of the organizing team)	3 + 3 (6)
	online participants	81
Total present at the meeting		99
Day 2	Total of participants in the discussion on Day 2, January 26, 2024	14 (13 in presence and 1 online)

The slides of the presentation from the 1st Day of the working group meeting, for which the consent by the speakers was received, were published on the E-RIHS and IPERION HS Zenodo communities. Link to the “workshops” section on IPERION HS website:

<https://www.iperionhs.eu/workshops/>

PROGRAMME (pag. 1 of 3)

Day 1: 25 January, Thursday, in presence and online

10:00 Meeting start

10:00-10:15 Luca Fontanesi, University of Bologna: Welcome address on behalf of the Rector of the University of Bologna

10:15-10:30 Maria Letizia Focarete, University of Bologna: Welcome address

Chairperson: Costanza Miliani

10:30-10:50 Rocco Mazzeo, University of Bologna: There cannot be a tip without an iceberg: career paths in Heritage science and discipline recognition

10:50-12:10 Matija Strlič, University of Ljubljana: Heritage science and their career paths through the eyes of heritage scientists

11:10-11:30 Break

Chairperson: Rocco Mazzeo

11:30-11:50 Costanza Miliani, ISPC-CNR: Crossing boundaries: Italian Heritage Science Excellence through interdisciplinary and intersectoral high education at E-RIHS national node

11:50-12:10 Vania Virgili, E-RIHS Implementation Phase: E-RIHS and the European Research Professional Landscape

12:10-12:30 Alison Heritage, ICCROM: Re-membling heritage science: who might be the future role-players?

12:30-14:00 Lunch (free)

PROGRAMME (pag. 2 of 3)

14:00-14:20 Antonina Chaban, CNR-INO: Current Topics in Heritage Science: analysing the HS Academy online lecture series

14:20-14:40 Josep Grau, University College London: Careers and scientific impacts of PhDs in Heritage Science: data and experiences from the UK (online)

14:40-15:00 Anna Pirri Valentini, Fondazione Scuola del Patrimonio: Educational and training gaps and needs for heritage professionals

15:00-15:20 Coffee break

Chairperson: Matija Strlič

15:20-15:40 Jon Yngve Hardeberg, Norwegian University of Science and Technology: Imaging for Cultural Heritage - experiences from the MSCA ITN project CHANGE

15:40-16:00 Francesca C. Izzo, Elisabetta Zendri, Ca' Foscari University of Venice: Training heritage scientists: from the classroom and laboratory to the profession- Experiences of graduates in Conservation Science and Technology for Cultural Heritage at Ca' Foscari University of Venice

16:00-16:20 Dafne Cimino, Italian Association of conservation scientists ANED BC: The role of scientists in the field of Cultural Heritage (online)

16:20-16:40 Caroline Mogenet, Fondation des sciences du Patrimoine: How to conduct an interdisciplinary research: the challenges of being a doctorate or post-doctorate student in heritage science

Closing of the first day sessions

PROGRAMME (pag. 3 of 3)

Day 2: 26 January, Friday, only in presence

Chairperson: Rocco Mazzeo

10:00-11:10 Summary report on the 1st day working group meeting, plenary discussion and preparation of the final document

11:10-11:30 Coffee break

11:30-13:00 Preparation and approval of the final document

13:00-13:15 Closing of the working group meeting

13:15 Meeting end

5 HS Academy Questionnaire

The purpose of the questionnaire was to explore the heritage science community, their places and nature of work, their interests and engagement with IPERION HS/E-RIHS and their identity. The questionnaire is available in the Appendix, such that it can be repeated in the future if desired.

The questionnaire was sent out via email through a professional network of people working in fields related to heritage science. The respondents were answering between November 2022 – February 2023. In total we collected 413 responses to the questionnaire.

5.1 Age

52% (215 out of 413) of participants were aged between 35-54 years; between them 25,5% aged 35-44 years and 26,2 % aged 45-54 years. Close were participants aged between 25-34 (23,1%), that can be marked as early career professionals; 55-64 (18,3%), the rest are represented by age groups 18-24, less than 18 or above 65 years (Figure 13).

Figure 13: HS Academy questionnaire respondent age distribution

5.2 Nationality and residency

Majority of participants (80%) were nationals of European countries, with a 13% representation of North (5%) and South Americans (8%). Among Europeans, the most respondents are nationals of Mediterranean countries (Spain, Italy, Portugal, France). The most Europeans answering were nationals of Spain (13%); Italy (12%); Portugal (10%), France (6%). Most participants (83%) are European residents (84%), followed by residents of South America 11%, North America (3%), Africa Asia Australia (all 1%). At the map below, we've shown the countries with minimal 1% or higher rate of responses from participants (4 or more, Figure 14).

Figure 14: HS Academy questionnaire respondent geographic distribution.

5.3 Education

Most represented educational level among participants was doctoral degree level – 60% among all respondents. This was followed by Master’s degree (27%), Bachelor’s degree and Professional degree (6%, Figure 15)

Figure 15: HS Academy questionnaire respondent educational level distribution.

Looking at all respondents per individual country and their education level, we can see below the distribution of countries with higher level of Doctoral degree holders and Master’s degree holders (Figure 16) in dark blue. However, it should be noted that in some countries the number of respondents was low (3 or less) and the results may not reflect the actual state of education level in those countries. The maps in Figure 16 should be compared to the map in Figure 14.

Figure 16: HS Academy questionnaire respondent doctoral and master's degree geographical distribution

5.4 Students and Young professionals (18-34)

Students and young professionals predominantly reside in their country of origin. Young professionals predominantly work (or study) at academic institutions (72,63%). A significant proportion (20%) work in the national level public sector (non-profit). The rest work in public local level institutions (3%) or museums and private (both 1%).

The most represented fields of work are conservation, chemistry and archaeology and archaeological science. 10% of respondents aged between 18-34 are working in other fields (Art, Art history, Anthropology, Biology, Climate science, Computer science, Law, Materials science, Medicine, Physics, Social science and economics). The majority of all respondents aged 18-34 work (or study) in the areas related to conservation (42%) (Fig. 5). 27% of all respondents aged 18-34 work in the field of chemistry. 21% of respondents aged between 18-34 years work in the field of archeology or archaeological science (Figure 17).

Figure 17: HS Academy questionnaire respondent field of work distribution

Among the respondents aged between 18-34, who work in the field of conservation, there are those, who work only in conservation (37%) or in combination chemistry-conservation (31%) or conservation related to archaeology and archaeological science (9%), while other combinations (conservation/restoration in combination represent 23% (Fig. 6).

Figure 18: HS Academy questionnaire respondents working in conservation in combination with other fields

5.5 Occupation

The most represented occupation group among respondents were Researchers in Science/Technology/Engineering/Mathematics (35%), followed by Conservators/restorers (20%), Researchers in Social Sciences/Humanities (13%), Teachers and other roles in education (11%) and students (8%), the rest were represented below 5% (Figure 19).

Figure 19: HS Academy questionnaire respondents occupations

5.6 Field of work

Almost half of respondents (50 %) are working at least partly in conservation related positions, followed by chemistry (27%), archaeology and archaeological science (25%), art history (9%), physics (7%), art (6%), building science and engineering (6%). Other subjects represent less than 5% each (Figure 20).

Figure 20: HS Academy questionnaire respondents fields of work

Most frequently occurs the combination of Chemistry and Conservation-Restoration (10%), followed by Archaeology and Conservation-Restoration (6%), Archaeology & archaeological science, Chemistry in 4%, Art history, Conservation-Restoration 3%, Building science and engineering and Conservation-Restoration 3%, Physics 2%, Art and Conservation-Restoration 2%, Art and Chemistry 2%. Other combinations represent less than 1%.

5.6.1 Conservation field

41% of respondents who work in the field of conservation or restoration and related fields, did not indicate specialization, 21% are specialized in Chemistry, 12% in Archaeology and Archaeological science, 6% in both Building science and engineering or Art, 2% are specialized in Physics. Other

specializations represent less than 1% of total Conservation and Restoration specialists. Others include Architecture & Urbanism, Ethics and philosophy, Social Science and economics, Anthropology, Biology, Climate science, and Data Science (Figure 21).

Figure 21: HS Academy questionnaire respondents in the field of conservation/restoration and their further specialisations

Among the respondents who indicated they work in conservation-restoration related field, we looked at the percentages of those who work in conservation-restoration field per country. We included countries who had at least 4 respondents or more. The highest rate among country respondents is Slovakia, where 91 % of all respondents works in conservation field. This is followed by Portugal (83%) Brazil (62,5%), Netherlands (61%); Sweden & USA (both 55%), France, Czechia, Greece (all 50%). The other countries have less than 50% respondents working in conservation related field (Figure 22).

Figure 22: HS Academy questionnaire respondents in the field of conservation/restoration and their country of residence (blue) compared to total country respondents (orange)

Conservators represent highly educated workers in heritage, 84% completed post graduate education. More than half (54%) of conservators hold a PhD or Master's (30%) degree and work in Academic or research institutions (Figure 23).

Figure 23: HS Academy questionnaire respondents in the field of conservation/restoration and their level of formal education

57% of all conservators work in academic or research institutions, 25% work in public or non-profit sector within a national body, 8% work in private sector, 6% work in Public or non-profit local authority institution, 4% are self-employed (Figure 24).

Figure 24: HS Academy questionnaire respondents in the field of conservation/restoration and their workplaces

5.6.2 Chemistry respondents

Among the respondents who indicated they work in chemistry related field, we looked at the percentages of those who work in chemistry field per country. We included countries who had at least 4 respondents or more. The highest rate among country respondents is Poland, where 78 % of all respondents works in chemistry field. This is followed by Serbia, (75 %), Czechia (67%) and the rest 50% or less (Figure 25).

Figure 25: HS Academy questionnaire respondents in the field of chemistry (blue) compared to total country respondents (orange)

77% of people working in chemistry related fields have PhD, 17% Masters degree. The majority (80%) work in Academic institutions (Figure 26).

Figure 26: HS Academy questionnaire respondents in the field of chemistry and their levels of education and places of work

5.6.3 Archaeology and archaeological science field

Among the respondents who indicated they work in archaeology and archaeological science related field, we looked at the percentages of those who work in this field per country. We included countries who had at least 4 respondents or more. The highest rate among country respondents is India, where all respondents work in archaeology related field. This is followed by Hungary and Denmark (80%) and the rest 50% or less (Figure 27). Those working in archaeology and related field in majority hold PhD (68,63%). The rest hold master's degree - 23,53%; bachelor's degree (4,90%)

or Professional degree (2,94%). Predominantly they work in Academic institutions 74,51% (Figure 28).

Figure 27: HS Academy questionnaire respondents in the field of archaeology or archaeological science (blue) compared to total country respondents (orange)

Figure 28: HS Academy questionnaire respondents in the fields of archaeology and archaeological science and their levels of education and places of work

Education-level-Archaeology-and-Archaeological-science-field

Archaeology-and-Archaeological-science-field-place-of-work

5.6.4 Heritage scientists

On average, respondents in the individual work fields of archaeology, chemistry and conservation-restoration 84% of respondents consider themselves to be heritage scientists (Figure 29).

Figure 29: HS Academy questionnaire respondents and their self-reported identity

5.6.5 Professional organizations

A total of 73 membership-based associations and organizations working in the field of heritage science were reported. Most people with membership in a professional organization come from Spain (15%), followed by Brazil (11%), Portugal (8%), Italy (7%), France, Germany, UK, USA (all 6%) and the rest represent less than 5% (Figure 30).

Figure 30: HS Academy questionnaire respondents belonging to membership organisations

56% of those with membership work in Academic or research institution, 24% in Public or non-profit sector - national body, 11% in Private sector (conservation). The rest is distributed among other types of workplaces.

Figure 31: HS Academy questionnaire respondents belonging to membership organisations and their places of work

5.7 Role in IPERION HS/E-RIHS

We asked participants about how they would like to be involved within the IPERION HS/ERIHS. The most interesting opportunity for engagement among respondents seems to be user engagement, represented in 34% of all answers. Other options were distributed between 10 and 16%. 14% of answers indicate interest in being members of the stakeholder community, 10% indicated interest to be involved in Iperion HS-ERIHS governance bodies or related and 12% indicated interest to be an access provider, 14% indicated not being engaged in any of the given options while 16% of answers indicates respondents do not know how they would be engaged (Figure 32).

Figure 32: HS Academy questionnaire respondents and their engagement in IPERION HS and/or E-RIHS

We further first looked at country distribution by the total number of responses and the national proportion of responses (Fig. 21), for respondents indicating an interest to become users. Since some countries had low number of respondents, we excluded those with less than 1% of responses (Figure 33).

Figure 33: HS Academy questionnaire respondents indicating an interest to become users, per country (excluding responses per country with less than 1% of responses)

65% of all indicating to be interested in becoming users are employed in academic or research institution, the rest from public or non-profit sector on national level (15%), Private sector in conservation (8%) and the rest distributed among other sectors (Figure 34).

Figure 34: HS Academy questionnaire respondents indicating an interest to become users and their places of work

We further analyzed those who indicated in interest to become access providers. There was a total of 12% respondents who would like to grant access. They come exclusively from academic or research institutions or Public or non-profit sector on national levels (Figure 35).

86% of people who indicated they would provide access come from Europe; 20% reside in Spain, 15% in Slovenia, 9% in United Kingdom, 6% in France or Netherlands and 5% in Italy or Portugal. The rest are below 5% (Fig. 23). 25% of participants of all participants coming from academic or research institutions or participants coming from public sector on national level or non-profit sector would be only offering access without using any services (Figure 36).

Figure 35: HS Academy questionnaire respondents indicating an interest to become access providers, per country

Figure 36: HS Academy questionnaire respondents indicating an interest to become access providers and their place of employment

Looking at the fields of disciplines, we see that 90% of people working in academic institutions in the archaeological field, 86% of people working in academic institutions in chemistry field and 70% of people working in academic institutions in conservation field would be prepared to grant access (Figure 37).

Figure 37: HS Academy questionnaire respondents indicating an interest to become access providers and their fields and places of employment

5.8 Time Available for Research

42% respondents dedicated to research most of the time, 16.2% more than half of the time, 16.2% up to half of the time (Figure 38).

Figure 38: HS Academy questionnaire respondents and availability to carry out research

Those who dedicate most of the time or more than half of the time to research work predominantly in academic or research institutions (80%) (Figure 39).

Figure 39: HS Academy questionnaire respondents devoting most time to research and their employment

Those spending most of the time researching, are working in archaeology (47%), conservation (34%) and chemistry (55%). More than a half of the time in research is spent by those working in archaeology field in 15%, while the proportion is 14% for those working in conservation field and 18% for those working in chemistry field (Figure 40).

Figure 40: HS Academy questionnaire respondents spending most time for research, per field

5.9 HS Academy and activities

Approximately 50% of respondents are aware of HS Academy activities. Those who are not aware, work mostly in academic or research institutions or in public or non-profit national level institutions. Among researchers and academics, about half are not aware of it, while among those working in national or non-profit national level bodies, more than half are aware of it. The level of unawareness is especially high among conservators working in private businesses and self-employed since they are not aware of it (both about two thirds).

Participants are most interested in online conferences followed by Online conferences, Webinars, Publication of technical notes/guidance documents/best practices, In-person/hands-on training, Online training (own time, i.e. asynchronous), In-person conferences, Online training (real time, i.e. synchronous), Development of teaching material, Online networking events, In-person networking events. The rest of activities were indicated as interesting by less than 5% (Figure 41).

Figure 41: HS Academy questionnaire respondents and their interests in IPHS activities

5.9.1 Academics and Researchers

Overall, those working in academia and research are most interested in online conferences, in-person/hands-on training; in-person conferences and in-person networking events.

5.9.2 Private sector conservation

Those who work in private sector related to conservation, have expressed most interest in online networking events in, followed by equal interest in publication of technical notes/guidance documents/best practices and online training (real time / i.e. synchronous).

5.9.3 Private sector (not conservation related)

Those working in private sector not related to conservation are most interested in online networking events, online conferences and development of teaching material.

5.9.4 Public or non-profit sector - national body

Those employed in national level organization or public bodies are most interested in online training in own time; followed by online conferences, online training in real time, publication of technical notes/guidance documents/best practices.

5.9.5 Public sector local authorities

Local level public sector employees are extremely interested in publication of technical notes/guidance documents/best practices; followed by webinars and online training in real time; and equally in online training in own time, development of teaching material and online conferences.

5.9.6 Self Employed

Self Employed are most interested in in-person or hands-on training, online conferences, online training (real time / i.e. synchronous), publication of technical notes/guidance documents/best practices and in-person conferences.

5.10 HS Academy events

55.3% of respondents have not attended any of the events, while 5,9 % have attended 3 events or more (Figure 42).

Figure 42: HS Academy questionnaire respondents and their attendance at IPHS events

The majority of those who attended the events, were from academia and research, followed by less than a quarter of participants working in public or non-profit sector on national level, private sector conservation, while others represented less than 5%.

50% of all participant academics, researchers and public or non-profit national level workers, non-conservation private sector attended at least 1 event. One third of participating private sector conservators, local authorities and self-employed attended at least one event.

Among reasons for not attending, almost all types of employees who did not attend any events indicated lack of awareness. Among those who attended 2 or more, time appeared as most frequent reason.

Overall, 35% of participants indicated time as the primary barrier, followed by lack of awareness 25%, funding 17%, not relevant- lack of interest 10 % and geography 8% (Figure 43).

Figure 43: HS Academy questionnaire respondents and their reasons for not attending IPHS events

5.11 Topics of interest for HS Academy activities

We analyzed the responses about the interest in current and prospective HS Academy activities through the Vitae framework model (Figure 44). The indicated activities were divided in 4 categories consisting of Knowledge and intellectual abilities; Engagement influence impact; Research governance and organisation; Personal effectiveness (development).

Figure 44: The VITAE transferable skills framework

The most interest shown was in category Knowledge and intellectual abilities. Majority of inputs indicated specific topics of interest in which the respondents would like to do research. Among the answers in the category Personal effectiveness, majority of answers indicated proposal for development of skills, that would impact their effectiveness in research, especially different kinds of trainings and seminars. In the category of Engagement, influence and impact, majority indicated the interest for interdisciplinary networking, citizen(public engagement and professional networking. In the category of Research governance and organoization, majority of answers covered management of digitalization processes in Cultural Heritage, developing the sectorial directions for the future, development of systemic access to facilities.

Figure 45: HS Academy questionnaire respondents and their interests in current or potential IPHS activities

5.12 Reinforcing Heritage Science Identity

The respondents were given a multiple-choice question on how they would see preferable methods of HS Identity reinforcement. Funding had the highest core since it was indicated in 13% of answers. It was followed by Conferences/networking events (11,74 %); Access to science facilities/infrastructure (11,69 %); Training and education (10,04 %); Professional organisation (e.g. Society of Heritage Scientists) (9,22 %); Formal heritage science education, e.g. BSc, MSc (8,57 %);

Access to literature/learning resources and Heritage science journals (peer reviewed; 8,10%) and Public engagement (6,75%). The rest were indicated below 5% (Figure 46).

Figure 46: HS Academy questionnaire respondents and their views of the potential for reinforcement of the HS identity

Figure 47: HS Academy questionnaire respondents' views of activities reinforcing the field of heritage science

Among those working in archaeology, the top 3 indicated activities to reinforce identity were access to infrastructure and facilities, funding and conferences or networking events. Those working in chemistry related fields find most important funding, access to facilities & infrastructures and formal heritage science education. Those working in conservation related fields find most important funding, training & education and access to science facilities & infrastructure (Figure 47).

Conclusion

The questionnaire conducted between November 2022 and February 2023 received 413 responses from respondents who are engaged in the field of heritage science. The Google form questionnaire was circulated among the respondents via link in an email and was promoted on social media platforms.

We received answers from European, North, and South American, Asian, and Australian respondents. However, most respondents were European residents, which is likely a reflection of the scope of ERIHS-IP network. Majority of respondents were those who are currently actively employed and work in conservation related field, followed by those working in chemistry and archaeology fields. These three groups were analysed more in depth, since their dominant presence was evident through the questionnaire analysis.

When analysing data in relation to residency we excluded the countries from which we received less than 1% of answers.

Majority of respondents hold undergraduate degrees and work in academia, research, or national level public bodies.

During the analysis of data on membership and existence of membership based national organizations, we observed that the respondents had some difficulty distinguishing between international organizations' national branches and individual national organizations.

Regarding the ERIHS activities, majority of those who are engaging are coming from academia and research. Reasons for lack of engagement are mainly lack of time or awareness.

In the future, respondents would prefer to be engaged predominantly in activities that increase knowledge and intellectual abilities. To increase the sense of heritage science identity, respondents would either need more access to funding and/or access to science facilities and infrastructure.

Appendix

1. HS demographics questionnaire

1. What is your age? *

- Less than 18 years
- 18— 24 years
- 25— 34 years
- 35 - 44 years
- 45 - 54 years
- 55 - 64 years
- 65— 74 years
- 75 years or older

2. What is your nationality? *

3. What is your (main) country of residence? *

4. What is the highest level of education you have completed *

- No schooling completed
- Nursery school to 8th grade
- High school diploma
- Associate degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Professional degree
- Doctorate degree

5. What is mainly your job role?

- Architectural conservator or equivalent
- Art/heritage dealer
- Conservator (Conservator-Restorer, Restorer or equivalent)
- Construction engineer
- Industry/business manager
- Museum curator, Archaeological site manager or equivalent R&D Manager
- Policy maker
- Researcher Engineering/IT
- Researcher Science/Technology/Engineering/Mathematics
- Researcher Social Science/ Humanities

- Retired (or otherwise not in employment)
- Student
- Teacher or other roles in education
- Urban planner

6. What field do you currently work in (max 2)

- Archaeology & archaeological science
- Anthropology
- Art
- Art history
- Biology
- Building science and engineering
- Chemistry
- Civil engineering (incl. optical, mechanical etc.)
- Climate science
- Conservation (Conservation-Restoration, Restoration or equivalent)
- Data Science
- Electronics and electrical engineering
- Ethics and philosophy
- Ethnology
- Health and wellbeing
- Information and computer science/engineering
- Law
- Mathematics
- Media
- Medicine
- Paleoanthropology and Paleontology
- Physics
- Social Science and economics

7. What best describes your place of employment? *

- Academic or research institution
- Public or non-profit sector - national body
- Public or non-profit sector - local authority
- Self employed
- Private sector (conservation)
- Private sector (not conservation related)
- Museum

8. If you are a member of a professional organization (e.g. society, association), please specify:

9. Would you describe yourself as a heritage science professional? For the definition of heritage science see: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Heritage_science

- Yes
- No

10. Is there a professional organisation (e.g. society or association) for heritage scientists in your country?

- No
- Yes
- If Yes, please specify

11. What is your role/how do you see yourself in relation to IPERION HS/E-RIHS * (tick all that apply)? If not familiar, please see https://www.per/onh*eu/ and <http://www.e-rihs.eu/>.

- User
- Access provider
- Member of IPERION HS/E-RIHS governance bodies or related
- Member of the stakeholder community
- None of the above I don't know
- Other

12. At work, how much time do you dedicate to scientific research (and related management or teaching activities)?

- Less than a quarter of my time
- Up to a Quarter of my time
- Up to a half of my time
- More than a half of my time
- Most of the time

13. Are you aware of the #HSAcademy, organized by IPERION HS/E-RIHS? *

- Yes
- No

14. What current or potential #HSAcademy activities are you interested in (max 5)? See <https://www.iperionhs.eu/academy-events/>

- Contribution to the organization of #HSAcademy activities
- Development of strategic direction for IPERION HS/E-RIHS Development of teaching material

- Delivery of #HSAcademy activities (e.g. training, webinars)
- In-person conferences
- In-person/hands-on training
- In-person networking events
- Online conferences
- Online networking events
- Online training (real time, i.e. synchronous)
- Publication of technical notes/guidance documents/best practices
- Social media activities
- Webinars
- None of the above/not interested

15. How many #HSAcademy events have you attended in the last year (meetings, webinars, summer schools etc.)?

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3+

16. If you would like to see more events/activities organized, what topics would you find of interest?

17. If you didn't attend as many #HSAcademy events as desired, what were the primary barriers (tick all that apply)?

- Funding
- Geography (too much travel, too big time difference)
- Lack of awareness Language
- Special access requirements Time
- Not relevant to me/lack of interest

18. Thinking of the field more generally, what could be done to reinforce a heritage science identity (max 5)?

- Access to literature/learning resources
- Access to science facilities/in*rastructure
- Conferences/networking events
- Develop an accreditation system
- Formal heritage science education, e.g. BSc, MSc Funding
- Heritage science journals (peer reviewed)
- Media engagement
- Professional organization (e.g. Society of Heritage Scientists)
- Public engagement
- Social media
- Technical/expert journals (not peer reviewed)
- Training and education